

NATIONAL ARCHITECTURE OF UZBEKISTAN AND ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF THE INDEPENDENCE PERIOD

Ismonov Xurshidbek Baxtiyorovich

Senior teacher of the Fine Arts and Music Education
Department of the Andijan State Pedagogical Institute.

E-mail: mr.ismonov@mail.ru

Raxmonov Saydullo Murodjon o'g'li

Student of Fine Art and Engineering
Graphics at Andijan State Pedagogical Institute.

E-mail: raxmonovsaydullo406@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article contains some information about the building of the first home in the world of the first world, the development of the consciousness of the people and the building of the sobstvennyh home from the first world, clay, brick and tomu podobogo. Predstavleny razlichnye drevneyshie memory art, discovered in the district, and historical architectural memory of the Togo period. More and more, ith the honor of independence, we can see that the national architecture is more developed, the construction of new modern denmarks is more developed. And at the same time we see that historical buildings are being restored.

A number of decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan provided information on the construction of modern houses, the restoration of old houses and the construction of new colleges and lyceums. And at the same time, some information is given about the construction of railroads between neighboring countries.

In the article, much attention was paid to the issues of architecture and urban planning. It is shown that after gaining independence, the construction of memorial buildings in the national style is getting more and more developed.

Key words: Minoray Kalon, Afrosiab, Varakhsha, Monumental, Tomb, Bashnya, Nakhshinkor, Poyi Kalon, architectural ensemble, engineering, architecture, decorative decoration, facade, plastic processing, ganch, wood carving.

The task of architecture is to organize a suitable spatial environment for human life and activity. This problem is solved by erected buildings and structures with a material structure. In the process of socio-ideological development of architecture, its functions and buildings are expressed in different ways through structures. With the honor of gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has entered a new era of its development. Our people have a rich historical, cultural and spiritual heritage. In addition to getting acquainted with the thousand-year history of architecture and urban planning, many opportunities were created not only to visit architectural monuments, but also to study and restore them.

Architecture of the primitive communal period. The beginning of construction activity dates back to the Paleolithic era. This period is associated with the reconstruction of the original settlements with simple stone tools in order to protect themselves from the inconvenience of the external environment and the impact of wild animals. In areas where there is a forest, cellars covered with branches, and separate standing cellars, consisting of gable or conical roofs, were arranged.

History of domestic architecture and monuments of architecture. It is said that architecture and construction on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan began in the 3rd millennium BC, and according to some sources, in the 10th millennium BC. Castles were built on hills and served as protection against external attacks. Today, the remains of about 400 fortresses have been preserved on the territory of Uzbekistan.

The oldest monuments of art discovered in Uzbekistan date back to the Mesolithic era. Examples of the Kaltaminor culture give an idea of the art of the Neolithic. A large stone statue of two snakes found in the Sokh of the Ferghana Valley, turned into a bracelet, with their heads facing each other, was created.

In the 1st millennium BC, real cities began to appear, such as Bactria, Sogd, Khorezm. Rectangular or round structures strengthened the walls of the fortress. Structures were built behind the wall that could provide shelter and protection for the inhabitants of the city during dangerous hostilities. In sculpture, limestone architectural decorations were used, which are found in abundance on the right bank of the middle Amu Darya. Sculptures made of clay and baked, as well as wall paintings testify to the high skill of Khorezm artists.

Archaeological excavations in Afrosiab, Varakhsh, Penjikent showed that residential buildings were built in a mixed order. The houses have 2-3 floors, are decorated with wood carvings, and the residential part is separated from the reception hall or hotel. Evidence of this is the image from the centuries-old history of architecture in the territory of Uzbekistan. Dome structures are widely used in monumental

buildings. Sometimes the walls of the building are made of mud bricks, the dome of the roof is made of baked bricks on the outside, or the wall of mud bricks is lined and strengthened with baked bricks.

The main square of Tashkent was built in 1966-1974. The main square of the capital has been completely renovated, the area of the square will be landscaped for people to relax. The main gate of the square is on the east side. In the south of the square, the Cabinet of Ministers was built, in the west - the buildings of the Senate, and in the north - a statue of the Sorrowful Mother and an architectural monument dedicated to the memory of the Uzbeks who heroically died during the Second World War. side.

Among the many buildings built in the center, the former 19-story building of the Ministry, which houses the museum, was reconstructed in 2006-2007 and several floors were demolished. The architecture is somewhat advanced, aesthetic qualities are important in construction.

With the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a new period of its development begins. Our people have a rich historical, cultural and spiritual heritage. The study and repair of architectural monuments developed at the level of restoration art.

The 2750 th anniversary of Samarkand, the 2500 th anniversary of Bukhara, Khiva and Termez, the 2700 th anniversary of Shakhrisabz, the 2200 th anniversary of Tashkent, the 2000 th anniversary of Margilan were celebrated. The great entrepreneur and famous statesman Amir Temur, the world-famous Alisher Navai, Abu Raykhan Beruni, Abu Ali-ibn Sina, al-Khorazmi, Ahmad Farghani, Marginani, Imam al-Bukhari, Bahauddin Naqshbandi, Abdukhalik Gijduvani, Steps of our compatriots, such as Najmuddin Kubro, Imam al-Moturdi, Jalaluddin Manguberdi have been updated to such an extent that they will become the heritage of our time for future generations. In 2007, the Khashtimorn mosque was built in Tashkent, which is recognized as the capital of Islamic culture and embodies the national decorative art.

Mausoleum of Ismail Somani. The introduction of Islam among the peoples of Central Asia, its formation as a state religion during the period of the Samanids and its transformation into a faith of the local population were reflected both in architecture and in construction. The use of domed structures is highly developed. On fig. 1 one of the rare and unique architectural monuments of great importance, preserved from that period, is the mausoleum of Ismail Somoni. All facades of the complex mausoleum are built in the same way. The walls are finished inside and out with high-quality baked bricks, and carving methods were also used during construction. There are many positive aspects in the use of domes, generated by necessity: at that time, there were

Picture 1.

practically no products and structures similar to reinforced concrete, which worked well in the bending parts of long-term structures. Sunlight falls directly on only one part of the domed roof and heats up that part very much, while radiation does not fall directly on the rest of the domed roof and the tower does not get very hot. This determined the further development of the creation of a new style, a new form and new solutions in the architecture of Central Asia.

Vremya stroitelstva Minaray Kalon, Minaray Kalon v Bukhara i period stroitelstva caravan-saraya Rabat Malik sootvetstvuyut karakhanidskomu period. Kalonskaya bashnya-one of high-quality production of world architecture and architectural design. The Poyi Kalon architectural ensemble was created. The minaret has a unique form, the sole is sharp, the body is conical, the kverhu sujaetsya, zakanchivaetsya kletkoy. Ego height is 50 m (in the middle is 46 m, in the middle is 47 m), the thickness is 0.8-0.9 m. glubina fundamenta do 10 m.

Picture 2.

The diameter of the circumference of the building in the Poipesh part is 9 m. Inside the tower there are 105 steps leading to the top of the tower along a spiral staircase-rotunda. At the top of the tower, 16 arched windows are installed to illuminate the staircase inside, through which one can observe the surroundings. On fig. 2 shows a general view of Kalon Minarai, built in 1127.

General view of the architectural ensemble of Poyi Kalon, including Minarai Kalon, in the background - Taki Zargaron, behind him on the left is the Ulugbek Madrasah and on the right is the Abdulazizkhan Madrasah. Poyi Kalon me Mori Ark Castle was built in the background.

Both the core and the decoration of the tower are made of brick (27x27x4-5 cm). Decorative bricks have different orientation and smooth surface. Flawless rings of various geometric shapes, stacked on top of each other, are framed by brick pediments.

Architecture of the period of independence of Uzbekistan.

After gaining independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 31, 1991, fundamental changes took place in all spheres of life. In 2002, the Urban Planning Code adopted by the Oliy Majlis came into force. On May 6, 2003, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the main directions for further deepening economic reforms in capital construction”, a number of resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers were adopted and the mechanism of the construction system was radically changed. The modern bridge across the Amu Darya was built to replace the 423-kilometer railway that ran through the territory of the neighboring country, the Navoi-Uchkuduk-Sultonuzdag-Nukus railway (358.1 km). It was put into operation in March 2004. As an example, we can see a modern bridge built across the Amu Darya.

After independence, due to the construction of a new modern railway, more than 20 million US dollars are saved per year from the expense of freight transportation within the republic, and more than 36 million US dollars, if international freight transportation is taken into account. The design length of this railway is 221.6 km. The design length of this railway is 221.6 km. The total length of the road is 123 km. This

Picture 3.

engineering structure went down in history as the first railway in Uzbekistan built in mountainous regions. Figure 3. The area with the new railway station in the city of Termez was built taking into account climatic conditions.

During the years of independence, modern and even cement concrete roads, 2.5 km long tunnels were built in the Kamchik and Rezak sections of the Tashkent-Osh highway, 94-214 km of roads were reconstructed. was built. On a winding, sloping road in the mountains

After gaining independence, wide avenues were opened for the development of national architecture and urban planning.

Picture 4.

Great importance was attached to the issues of architecture and urban planning.

In the city of Tashkent, in the area where the historical madrasah of Barakkhan is located, our people were presented with a majestic building in the national style - the architectural ensemble of Khazrat Imam. It should be noted that the construction of this new mosque was completed in just 100 days. It is included in the UNESCO list of historical cities, priceless for all mankind. In 2007, the city of Tashkent was declared the capital of Islamic culture. General view of the

Hazrat Imam mosque, recently built in the national style in Tashkent. Internal view of the dome with a dome made in the form of a drum in the national style.

Statues of Amir Temur were installed in the cities of Tashkent, Shakhrisabz and Samarkand. In Figure 4, in the design of these structures, traditional forms were used and developed (arch, volume of the shell, dome, etc.), the art of creating gardens was improved, the historical and traditional connection between architecture and art developed (decorative finishing, plastic processing of facades, ganch, carving on tree, etc.). We can see the statue of Amir Temur installed in the cities of Tashkent, Shakhrisabz and Samarkand.

In 1988, the 1225th anniversary of the birth of the great scholar Imam al-Bukhari, who made a great contribution to the world Islamic culture, was celebrated. On the initiative and under the leadership of the President, in the footsteps of Alloma, located in the village of Khoja Ismail Eski, Khartang, Poyaryk district, a huge complex in the national style was built. The mausoleum of Imam al-Bukhari in the Memori complex was built in a modern national style.

This indoor tennis court for 3000 seats near the Tashkent TV tower with a unique architectural and constructive solution is one of the best sports facilities in the world with a unique architectural and functional solution. The appearance of an indoor tennis court without columns in Tashkent is a TV tower. The tennis court is made in a unique form, convenient for spotters, fans, visitors and various events.

On the initiative and direct leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a completely new Independence Square was created in terms of content and form. The buildings of the Cabinet of Ministers and the Ministry of Finance have been completely reconstructed. The majestic building of the Senate, which absorbed elements of Uzbek national architecture, gave special architectural significance to the main square of the capital of Uzbekistan.

Picture 5.

The square composition had a peculiar appearance and was the center of the architectural composition.

The "Arch of Virtue" was built at the entrance to the main square in Tashkent of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A white corridor leads to a majestic arch connecting sixteen marble columns. Cranes circled above, carefree storks were skillfully portrayed. The "Monument of Independence", a symbolic symbol of the globe, erected in the first days of independence, has become a vivid expression of the emergence in the world of a new country called Uzbekistan, the achievement of true freedom by the Uzbek people. The sixteen-column arch of virtue on Independence Square is a symbol of peace and tranquility.

Picture 6.

As a sign of republican youth, a symbol of goodness, this monument was decorated with a bronze statue "Happy Mother", depicting a mother and child. The main square of the Monument of Independence and Virtue will be built.

Monument of Independence and Virtue on

Republic Square. The Virtue Arc opened a new field content.

It has become a symbol of the pure and noble goals of independent Uzbekistan. Many fountains are designed to improve the microclimate. On the northern side of Independence Square, there is a Memorial Square dedicated to our compatriots who died during the Great Patriotic War, with a statue of the Sorrowful Mother. (Figure 6).

In connection with the creation of the National Park named after Alisher Navoi (1991-1994), one of the central squares of the city of Tashkent was completely reconstructed. Here, the events of the Independence and Navruz holidays are solemnly recreated in a form convenient for eight people. The purpose of the reconstruction of the national park named after Alisher Navoi was to create comfortable conditions for the recreation of residents and guests of the city. At the suggestion of the President, an exhibition pavilion for fine and applied arts, exhibitions of clothing models and other purposes was built on the western side of the park, that is, in a quiet place of rest.

Summary

The national architectural art of Uzbekistan developed rapidly. New hidden aspects of architecture have been discovered. Taking into account the achievements of the architecture of developed democratic countries, modern building materials such as metal, concrete, brick, wood, plastic, glass and other modern materials and structures are used in our country with the honor of independence. New buildings and structures were built and reconstruction work was launched, architectural monuments were restored in a new style and radically improved. Architects, skillfully combining

national conditions and traditional modern styles, built buildings from traditional and modern structures and materials. Buildings that have stood the test of time have begun to be built after relentless research.

The construction of strong, proud buildings and structures that will serve future generations, modern and comfortable housing, vocational colleges, academic lyceums, in order to make our cities and villages more beautiful and prosperous, and similar buildings were erected in a new style.

REFERENCES:

1. Mirzaev Sh.R. M. M. Vakhitov. Architecture part 1. Tashkent, 2012.
2. Mirzaev Sh.R. M. M. Vakhitov. Architecture part 2. Tashkent, 2012.
3. Vakhitov M.M. Sh. R. Mirzaev. Architecture part 3. Tashkent, 2012.
4. Apukhtin O.K. Fundamentals of fine arts. Tashkent, 1967.
5. Vakhidov M.M. Sh. R. Mirzaev. Buildings and constructions. Tashkent, Trud, 2003.
6. Vakhidov M.M. Architectural monuments of Bukhara. Bukhara, 2009.
7. Vakhidov M.M. National architecture of Uzbekistan. Bukhara, 2009.
8. Azimov I.M. Patterns of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, publishing house of literature and art. G'Guloma, 1987.
9. Vakhidov M.M. Architectural monuments of Khiva. Bukhara, 2009.
10. Teshaboev R.D. Architectural structures and parts of civil buildings. Tashkent, teacher, 2012.
11. Architecture and construction of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2006, No. 3.
12. Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, volumes 1-14. Tashkent, 1971-1980